

AERODYNAMICS STUDIES OF VARIOUS PASSENGER VEHICLES USING COMPUTATIONAL FLUID DYNAMICS (CFD)

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ABSTRACT

This research work explores the aerodynamic characteristics of various automobiles, specifically passenger vehicles like sedans, SUVs, and hatchbacks, utilizing computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations and performing practical experimentation using wind tunnel. Previous studies on this topic were not able to give a comparative aerodynamic analysis of different automotive body type of automobiles. The study focuses on comparing the pressure distribution on the body of each vehicle type due to aerodynamic forces to gain insights into their aerodynamic performance and will help determine the efficient aerodynamics and how it causes a reduction in drag forces when compared with a general passenger car. The primary objective is to investigate the influence of different vehicle geometries on aerodynamic performance. The findings aim to contribute valuable insights for optimizing automobile design to enhance fuel efficiency and overall performance.

Keywords: CFD, Aerodynamics, Drag, Lift, Wind Tunnel

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INTRODUCTION

The automotive industry is continuously evolving to meet the demands of sustainability and efficiency. Aerodynamics plays a pivotal role in achieving these goals, impacting fuel consumption and vehicle stability. The science of aerodynamics examines how air flows around objects. Aerodynamics, as it relates to automobiles, is concerned with how air flows around and through vehicles and how this affects their handling, performance, and fuel efficiency. Automobile aerodynamics is an important aspect for the design of all types of vehicles, from passenger cars to trucks to racing cars. For high-performance vehicles, aerodynamics can be critical to achieving top speeds and lap times.

Senthilkumar (2022) et al. explored the aerodynamic performance of a car by comparing models equipped with no diffuser, a standard diffuser, and an enhanced diffuser [1]. Their findings indicated that the modified diffuser could significantly lower the drag and lift coefficients relative to the conventional diffuser. Naidu's (2023) study delved into how various design elements of a vehicle affect its aerodynamic drag, focusing on the impact of different diffuser angles on drag and turbulent kinetic energy [2]. Ljungskog et al. (2020) conducted a detailed examination of how incorporating the specifics of wind tunnel design and boundary conditions into computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations can affect the predictions of aerodynamic forces on sedan-type vehicles. They found that including these details can lead to highly accurate predictions of the drag coefficient when compared to direct wind tunnel measurements without corrections [3]. Gunpinar and his team (2019) introduced a design support tool aimed at estimating the drag coefficient based on the vehicle's side silhouette, employing Gunpinar's technique for silhouette representation [4]. Khaligh and colleagues (2012) detailed the use and effectiveness of a Cartesian RANS simulation approach, leveraging the Immersed Boundary method, to assess aerodynamic flow around SUVs [5]. Selvaraju et al. (2022) established that the aerodynamic forces acting on a vehicle are significantly influenced by the distribution of pressure across its surfaces, noting that variations in pressure at the front and rear ends lead to drag due to the pressure differential [6].

The main aerodynamic forces acting on a vehicle are Drag, Lift and Down-force. Drag is the force that opposes the forward motion of the vehicle. It is caused by the air resistance to the vehicle's shape. Drag is the largest aerodynamic force acting on a vehicle, and it increases with the square of the vehicle's speed. Lift is a force that acts perpendicular to the direction of travel. It is caused by the difference in air pressure between the top and bottom of the vehicle. Lift can cause the vehicle to become airborne at high speeds, which can lead to instability. Down-force is a force that acts downward on the vehicle. It is used to improve traction and handling, especially at high speeds. Down-force is generated by aerodynamic features such as spoilers and wings.

ANSYS FLUENT was used to do the CFD Simulations and plot the pressure contours of the various automobile design types.

METHODOLOGY

Background Theory and Experimental Setup

Comparative examination of various automobile bodies through Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) for maximizing fuel efficiency is the main motive by the researchers in this study. The purpose of studying aerodynamics of various automobile forms is to create designs that not only slice through the air with little resistance but also improve overall speed and handling, particularly in high-performance circumstances. Wind tunnels are the primary tools used for the purpose of measuring the air and velocity around the object. A wind tunnel is a controlled environment where the aerodynamic properties of objects, like car models, can be tested. Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) involves using computer simulations to analyze fluid flow around these models. Combining both methods provides a comprehensive understanding of aerodynamics. By testing various car body types in a wind tunnel and comparing them through CFD simulations, engineers can gather data on factors like drag, lift, and turbulence.

Drag Force: The force preventing the car from moving forward due to air around is called Drag. This is so that, car's shape stays intact by air. The largest aerodynamics force operating on a vehicle is called drag and it rises as vehicle's speed is squared.

$$F_D = \frac{1}{2} \rho V^2 C_D A$$

Lift Force: It is the force that acts perpendicular to the direction of motion. It is due to the difference in air pressure between the top and bottom of the vehicle. Lift can cause the vehicle to become airborne at high speeds, which can lead to instability.

$$L = C_L \left(\frac{1}{2} \rho V^2 \right) A$$

Down-force: It is a crucial concept in automotive engineering, representing the force that pushes a vehicle's tires onto the road surface, enhancing traction and stability. Achieved through careful design of a car's body and aerodynamic elements, down-force is essential for optimizing performance, especially at high speeds and during dynamic maneuvers. By manipulating the airflow around the vehicle, engineers can generate a downward force that counters the tendency of the car to lift, promoting better grip and contact between the tires and the road. This not only improves cornering capabilities but also enhances overall control and safety. The careful balance between down-force and aerodynamic drag is a delicate dance, as designers strive to maximize the benefits of increased traction without compromising speed.

DEVELOPMENT OF WIND TUNNEL FOR TESTING

The development of wind tunnel started by designing the basic structure and components of wind tunnel. Firstly, a basic CAD design is made using SolidWorks (refer Figure 1 & 2) to visualize the various component sizing and scaling. This is to ensure the scaling to be done with Tesla Cyber truck CAD model, to be 3D printed for the wind tunnel testing.

Figure 1: CAD model of wind tunnel.

Figure 2: CAD Model of wind tunnel with arrangement for laminar flow and fan coupled with a BLDC motor.

A scaled-down model of Tesla Cybertruck (refer Figure 3) was 3D-printed using PLA filament to visualize the air flow patterns around the car-body, approx. dimensions of the model were 22.8 cms x 9.3cms x 7.53cms.

Figure 3: 3D-Printed model of Tesla' cybertruck model.

Components used in the wind tunnel were selected to maintain the structural integrity as there are some vibrations because of powered BLDC motor. Four 50 cms x 22cms plywood pieces are used to make the enclosed frame of the wind-tunnel. This is done to make sure that the frame of wind tunnel can easily take up forces and vibrations of BLDC motor at high speeds.

Figure 4: Laminar flow arrangement made from paper straws.

A structure was fabricated using straw pipes to convert the turbulent flow of smog into streamline flow as shown in Figure 4 above. This was made using straw pipes piled one over the another in a mesh like structure. During the testing phase it was observed that paper exhibits less resistance to air-flow w.r.t that of rubber straw.

The BLDC motor controller was used to manage the speed of the BLDC motor, managing the motor's speed, direction, and overall performance through precise electronic control. A potentiometer, in this context, serves as an input device, providing variable resistance to regulate and fine-tune the speed or position of the BLDC motor by adjusting the voltage supplied to the controller.

Smog generator is made using a hair dryer and glycerol dipped cotton, which when heated inside the body of hair dryer produces cloudy smog that can be utilized to visualize the contour of air flow during wind-tunnel testing.

Wind Tunnel Assembly

Assembly of wind tunnel is done with the consideration of frame length to fit in any type of scaled-down model with ease and also to get a better view of air-flow patterns, one of the frame is cut out and is covered with acrylic sheets to fill any air gaps. The air-straightener is made using paper straws of 8 mm diameter and are placed layer by layer to get minimum air-friction by the air-straightener.

1. **Frame Construction:** Use plywood to construct the frame of the wind tunnel. Design it with a streamlined shape to minimize air turbulence. Ensure a long and straight test section for accurate aerodynamic measurements.
2. **Fan Installation:** Mounted a BLDC motor-controlled exhaust fan at one end of the wind tunnel to generate airflow. Ensure that the fan is securely attached to avoid vibrations.
3. **Laminar flow arrangement:** Installed the structure using straw pipes, downstream of the fan to create a more uniform and laminar airflow. This can also be a honeycomb structure or a series of guide vanes to smoothen the air flow the air.
4. **Test Section Integration:** Include a test section in the middle of the wind tunnel where models or objects can be placed for aerodynamic analysis.
5. **Variable Speed Control:** Implement a variable speed control for the BLDC fan to adjust the airflow velocity according to testing requirements.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

While performing the Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) Analysis on Tesla Cybertruck, the below depicted Pressure Contours and velocity streamlines were observed. The speed range was taken between 50km/h to 175km/h, with intervals at 80km/h, 120km/h and 150km/h. The minimum and maximum pressure were found to be 430Pa, 2051 Pa at speeds of 50 km/h, 175 km/h respectively.

Figure 5: Pressure contour at different velocities of Tesla Cybertruck and velocity streamlines.

While performing the CFD analysis on the Generic SUV, the pressure contours and velocity streamlines shown in Figure 5 were observed. The speed range was taken between 50 km/h to 175 km/h, with intervals at 80 km/h, 120 km/h and 150 km/h. The minimum and maximum pressure were found to be 597 Pa, 2845 Pa at speeds of 50 km/h, 175 km/h respectively.

Figure 6: Pressure contour at different velocities of Generic SUV and velocity streamlines.

While performing the CFD analysis on the Tesla Model S, the pressure contours and velocity streamlines shown in Figure 6 were observed. The speed range was taken between 50 km/h to 175 km/h, with intervals at 80 km/h, 120 km/h and 150 km/h. The minimum and maximum pressure were found to be 138 Pa, 1722 Pa at speeds of 50 km/h, 175 km/h respectively.

Figure 7: Pressure contour at different velocities of Tesla Model S and velocity streamlines.

Table 1: Tabular Data of Maximum Pressure (Pa)

SPEED	Peak Pressure on vehicle body		
	Cybertruck	Generic SUV	Tesla Model S
50 km/h	167 Pa	238 Pa	138 Pa
80 km/h	430 Pa	597 Pa	399 Pa
120 km/h	965 Pa	1340 Pa	804 Pa
150 km/h	1504 Pa	2086 Pa	1288 Pa
175 km/h	2051 Pa	2845 Pa	1722 Pa

Table 1 summarizes the speeds and respective maximum pressure of the three passenger vehicles that have been considered for analysis. As can easily be inferred from the Table 1 clearly, Tesla Model S, which is a sedan has the best aerodynamic shape as the pressure exerted at the front of it is the least (1722 Pa) at the maximum speed of 175 km/h as compared with Tesla Cybertruck and Generic SUV.

The Generic SUV, however, has the least aerodynamic shape among the three automobiles as the pressure exerted at the front of it is the most 2845 Pa at the maximum speed of 175 km/h.

However, the Cybertruck has data in between the above two mentioned automobiles with maximum pressure of 2051 Pa at top speed of 175 km/h. Therefore, efforts can be made to improve its aerodynamic shape and make it at par with Tesla Model S. The comparative graph of the above results is also plotted in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Pressure vs velocity plot of different car bodies.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS & ANALYSIS

After flow analysis of cybertruck in the wind tunnel following air flow patterns are observed at different speeds. As can be observed, flow lines are smooth over the entire body but a separating region has been made in front of the bumper which separates the flow of air over and below the body of the truck. The reason of maximum pressure is at the front of the truck i.e., over the bumper since the bumper comes in contact with the air first as compared to the rest of the automobile body.

Figure 9: Results of experimental airflow around Cybertruck

CONCLUSION & DISCUSSION

Using CFD simulation is not enough to verify the results of analysis. It can be seen that even though CFD can provide a wide variety of options to simulate under various external conditions and air-flows, it is also required to experimentally validate the same using a wind tunnel, which have a variable speed exhaust coupled fan that can help us visualize the air-flow patterns around any scaled-down 3D-printed model. While doing CFD analysis of different automotive bodies it is found that Cybertruck performs well under the constraints of turbulent flow i.e. K- ϵ Viscous model than a generic SUV and the maximum pressure due to wind is seen on the front bumper portion of the vehicle. Again, experimenting with the wind tunnel on Cybertruck using the wind tunnel helps to validate the patterns and contour of air-flows around the model. This is done by slowly varying the exhaust fan speed using a knob potentiometer.

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